

Operational Impacts of the U.S. Federal Aviation Administration and the U.S. Laser Clearinghouse on an Optical Communications Earth Relay

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Abstract— NASA is planning to launch the next generation of a space-based Earth relay satellite sometime in the middle of the next decade to join the current Space Network, consisting of Tracking and Data Relay Satellites in space and the corresponding infrastructure on Earth. While the requirements and architecture for that relay satellite are unknown at this time, NASA is investing in communications technologies that could be deployed to provide new communications services. One of those new technologies is optical communications. The Laser Communications Relay Demonstration (LCRD) project, scheduled for launch in 2019 as a hosted payload, is a critical pathfinder towards NASA providing optical communications services on the next generation space-based relay. This paper will describe the concept of operations and the impacts of the U.S. Federal Aviation Administration and the U.S. Laser Clearinghouse on the Laser Communications Relay Demonstration. It will provide a high level overview of the link budgets and discuss the analysis done on both space to ground links and geostationary (GEO) to low Earth orbit (LEO) links. The U.S. Laser Clearinghouse is a United States Air Force Strategic Command organization that provides predictive avoidance analysis and deconfliction with U.S. and allies satellites and operations. NASA’s policy is to be in compliant with the U.S. Laser Clearinghouse. Having a valid concept of operations that is compliant with the U.S. Federal Aviation Administration and the U.S. Laser Clearinghouse is critical to making optical communications a reality on future NASA science and exploration missions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

One of the mission critical functions a satellite has to perform is communicating with its mission operations center. Such a communications link is needed for command and control of the satellite as well as transmitting mission data back to Earth. Sometimes, information from a space-base data observing, scientific, or exploration mission must be returned to Earth with as low latency as possible. For example, low latency and high availability is extremely important for human exploration missions. Earth relay satellites are satellites placed in geostationary orbit (GEO) to relay information to and from non-GEO satellites, aircraft, scientific balloons, and Earth stations that otherwise would not be able to communicate at all or would not be able to communicate for long periods of time. A network of Earth relay satellites increases the amount of time that a spacecraft in Earth orbit, especially in low Earth orbit (LEO), can be in communications with a mission operations center.

NASA’s Goddard Space Flight Center operates the Space Network for the Space Communications and Navigation office within NASA. The Space Network is a series of Earth relay satellites in GEO with the associated ground stations and operation centers. There are currently three different generations of spacecraft in orbit, referred to as Tracking and Data Relay System Satellites, and NASA is studying the requirements for a future generation to be launched around the 2025 timeframe.

NASA is in the process of determining the future architecture, capabilities, and services of the future Space Network. While the exact requirements are currently unknown, NASA is investing in communications technologies that could be deployed on the satellite to provide new communications services. One of those new technologies is optical communications.

Several space agencies are currently working on space-based optical communications. The primary motivation stems from the expectation that substantially higher (at least 10 times) data rates than Radio Frequency (RF) based solutions might

be feasible with similar user spacecraft onboard terminal burden (mass, volume and power). In addition, optical communications can also be used at comparable RF data rates in order to lower the user communication system's required mass, volume, and power. Finally available RF spectrum is also becoming an issue in high data rate applications.

2. THE LASER COMMUNICATIONS RELAY DEMONSTRATION

In order to gain more knowledge and experience in the area of space-based optical communications relay services, NASA is embarking on the Laser Communications Relay Demonstration (LCRD) to launch as a hosted payload [1]. LCRD is a joint project between NASA Goddard Space Flight Center, NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory, and MIT Lincoln Laboratory. The demonstration will provide at least two years of high rate optical communications from geostationary orbit to two ground stations located in the United States. NASA is also considering flying an optical communications terminal on a Low Earth Orbit (LEO) spacecraft, such as the International Space Station, to test inter-satellite links with LCRD.

To make optical communications truly available to NASA future projects, long mission life space terminals must be proven. In addition, optical communications through Earth's atmosphere, such as via a space to ground link, requires a robust operational concept for reliable high-rate data delivery in the face of terrestrial weather variations. Future optical communications operations will also have to be compliant with U.S. Federal Aviation Administration policies and regulations. In addition, there are also policies, regulations, and procedures required by the U.S. Laser Clearinghouse that NASA has agreed to adhere to. To increase the availability of a space to ground optical communications link, which is impacted by clouds, there needs to be a demonstration of handover among multiple ground sites. For Near Earth applications, a demonstration needs to show the relaying of an optical communications signal in space. There also needs to be a demonstration of the modulation and coding suitable for very high rate links.

LCRD's flight payload consists of two optical communications terminals in space with a switch between them. A single optical communications terminal on LCRD consists of an optical module (a telescope or head), a modem, and an optical module controller.

Each optical module, shown in Figure 1, is a 4-inch reflective telescope that produces a ~15 microradian downlink beam. It also houses a spatial acquisition detector which is a simple quadrant detector, with a field of view of approximately 1 milliradian. It is used both for detection and coarse tracking of an uplink signal. The telescope is mounted to a two-axis gimbal via a magnetohydrodynamic inertial reference unit (MIRU). Angle-rate sensors in the MIRU detect angular disturbances which are then rejected using voice-coil actuators for inertial stabilization of the telescope. Optical fibers couple the optical module to the modems where

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transmitted optical waveforms are processed. Control for each optical module and its corresponding modems are provided by a controller. Each optical module is held and protected during launch with a cover and one-time launch latch.

Figure 1 – Inertially Stabilized Optical Module

The LCRD Ground Segment is comprised of the LCRD Mission Operations Center (LMOC) and two ground stations: Ground Station 1 and Ground Station 2. The LMOC will perform all scheduling, command, and control of the LCRD payload and the ground stations. The LMOC is connected with all other segments, and communicates with the two ground stations using high capacity terrestrial connections. Connection to the space segment will be provided either through one of the ground stations, or through a lower capacity connection to the host spacecraft's Mission Operations Center (HMOC) and then to the LCRD flight payload by the spacecraft's RF link. This architecture will allow the mission to demonstrate:

- Demonstrate high rate 24/7 optical communications operations over a 2 year period from GEO to Earth
- Demonstrate real-time optical relay from one Ground Station through the GEO flight payload to the second Ground Station
- Use both a Near Earth (DPSK) and a Deep Space (PPM) compatible modulation and coding
- Demonstrate 1.244 Gbps (2.880 Gbps uncoded) uplink and downlink using Differential Phase Shift Keying (DPSK)
- Demonstrate 311 Mbps uplink and downlink using Pulse Position Modulation (PPM)
- Demonstrate the Next Generation TDRS compatible optical terminal capable of supporting both Direct to Earth and GEO to LEO (ISS Terminal) communications
- Demonstrate operational concepts for reliable, high-rate data delivery in face of terrestrial weather variations typically encountered by real NASA missions
- Demonstrate control of handover among ground sites

- Performance testing and demonstrations of coding and link layer protocols over optical links with an orbiting testbed

LCRD will support differential phase shift keying (DPSK) which can be used at extremely high data rates and has sufficient background tolerance to support communications when the sun is in the field of view. LCRD leverages a DPSK modem previously designed by MIT Lincoln Laboratory [2] as a cost effective approach to providing a DPSK signal. It can both transmit and receive, supporting data rates from 2 Mbps to 1.24 Gbps. Reduced data rates are achieved efficiently via a “burst mode” format, with data bursts interspersed with “dead times” where no signal is transmitted. In future relay scenarios, the modem could be replaced by a higher rate DPSK modem that would support data rates beyond 10 Gbps. In addition to DPSK, LCRD will also support pulse position modulation (PPM). The transmitter will utilize the same 2.88 GHz clock rate, and modulate the signal with a sequence of 16-ary PPM symbols (a signal pulse is placed in exactly one of each 16 temporal slots). The maximum PPM data rate is 311 Mbps.

Figure 2 – Ground Station 1, OCTL Site, Table Mountain, CA

NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory will enhance its Optical Communications Telescope Laboratory (OCTL) so that it can be used as Ground Station 1 of the demonstration. The OCTL is located on top of Table Mountain in the San Gabriel Mountains of southern California and houses a 1-m $f\#75.8$ coude focus telescope; it is shown in Figure 2 above. The large aperture readily supports the high data rate DPSK and PPM downlinks from the LCRD space terminal with adequate link margin. Required to operate 24/7, in the presence of winds, and as close as 5 degrees solar angles, the OCTL telescope shown in Figure 1 will be enclosed in a temperature controlled dome with a transparent window to allow laser beam and radar transmission [3].

MIT Lincoln Laboratory is developing a second optical communications ground station, referred to as Ground Station 2 within LCRD. Ground Station 2 will have a 60 cm receive aperture, a 15 cm transmit aperture, and be located within an approximately 5.5 meter diameter dome on one of the islands in Hawaii; ideally it will be located at a summit of one of the volcanoes there to get above the clouds and have excellent atmospheric seeing conditions. NASA has been specifically studying Haleakala, a dormant volcano on the island of Maui, Mauna Kea and Mauna Loa, on the Big Island.

Figure 3 – Ground Station 2 Site Telescope and Dome

The laser subsystem consists of a custom photonics assembly that produces a low power (<10 mW) fiber-coupled optical signal, followed by a commercially obtained high-power optical amplifier. The fiber amplifier can produce up to 10 W of optical power but will be limited by software to a maximum power of 7.3 W during operation. After accounting for transmission loss of the transmit telescope and the window in the dome, the maximum power emitted into free space outside the dome is 5.4 W.

3. LINK BUDGETS

The future Earth relay satellite will provide at least two optical links to perform a relay service: one is from the user platform, typically in LEO for NASA scenarios, to the relay satellite and the second is from the relay satellite to the ground (4). In the case of LCRD, both links will be operating in the optical communications C-band.

The LCRD’s Earth relay will include two identical optical terminals: each with 10.7 cm aperture and $\frac{1}{2}$ W of transmit optical power.

For this analysis we assumed a LEO terminal with identical aperture size (10.7 cm) and somewhat larger optical power (~3W). Ground station is a 1 meter telescope located on Table

Mountain in California, US. It includes an adaptive optics system to mitigate atmospheric turbulence.

Figure 4 - LCRD Concept

The LCRD relay link will include Forward Error Correction (FEC) coding and interleaving to mitigate communication channel impairments. Coding and interleaving will be implemented at the link edges: at LEO terminal and at the ground station. The need for coding and interleaving comes from the desire to improve the error statistics of the communication relay link. These are being impacted by various random and deterministic impairments. Chief among them, atmospheric fading, is capable of introducing significant bursts of errors at the receiver [4]. LCRD selected coding is the industry standard DVB-S2 with the convolutional interleaving up to one second long.

Analysis of the two relay links, operating at highest user data rate, is shown in ERROR! REFERENCE SOURCE NOT FOUND.. For this analysis we have considered the longest possible distance between LEO and GEO terminals (~46 Mm). The Earth relay satellite position was chosen at 63 degrees west, which corresponds to a 20 degree link elevation angle over the horizon – the stressed condition for LCRD highest data rate. The operation at lower elevation angles is enabled by lowering down the data rate. That is, LCRD is capable to adapt to atmospheric conditions by adjusting its user data rates within 1,244 Mbps to 2 Mbps range [5]. Links in Table 1 are constructed for 1.244 Gbps data rate.

Both, the LEO to GEO and the GEO to Ground links have an adequate link margins to close the entire relay link at highest data rate.

4. FAA AND AIRCRAFT SAFETY

FAA policies on laser use within FAA airspace are based largely on the safety guidelines set forth in the ANSI Z136.6: American National Standard for Safe Use of Lasers Outdoors. This standard is a product of the SAE G10-T Laser Safety Hazards Committee and provides guidelines for mitigating the hazards associated with operating laser systems outdoors. The ANSI Z136.6 also details how to calculate the Maximum Permissible Exposure (MPE) of a given laser. In order to ensure no injury is caused by a laser, no person should be exposed to more than the MPE for that laser.

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	LEO->GEO	GEO->GND
LINK PARAMETER	dB	dB
Transmitter		
Modem Out Ave Power (dBW)	4.77	-3.01
Tx Optical Loss	-5.24	-5.24
Tx Pointing Loss	-1.01	-1.01
Tx Gain	106.77	106.77
Modem TX Impl. Penalty	-1.50	-1.50
EIRP (dBW)	103.79	96.01
Path		
Range Loss	-291.49	-290.09
Atmospheric Loss	0	-0.57
Atm Strehl Loss	0	0
PFD (dBW/m²)	-59.12	-67.47
Receiver		
Rx Antenna Gain	106.77	125.96
Rx Pointing Loss	-0.85	0
Rx Optical Loss	-5.10	-9.94
Modem Input Power (dBW)	-86.88	-78.63
Modem RX Impl. Penalty	-2.00	-2.00
Photon Energy (dBJ)	188.95	188.92
Slot Rate (dB-Slot/s)	-94.59	-94.59
Code Rate	3.01	3.01
Codec/interleaver Impl. Losses	0	-0.55
Received Photon per Bit (dB ph/b)	8.48	16.16
Required Photon per Bit (dB ph/b)	6.00	10.00
MARGIN (dB)	2.48	6.16

Table 1 - LEO to GEO Relay and GEO Relay to Ground Terminal link budgets

For lasers with visible and infra-red wavelengths shorter than 1400nm, the optics of the eye focus the light to a small point on the retina, greatly increasing the potential for damage. As a result, the MPE for these wavelengths is of the order of 1mW/cm2.

Lasers with wavelengths greater than 1400nm, however, cannot be transmitted by the cornea and lens of the eye and therefore cannot be focused on the retina. The concern for these longer wavelengths is purely thermal. The MPE for the “eye-safe” wavelengths is set so as to prevent thermal damage to tissues. This results in the ANSI standards setting the MPE for a wavelength of 1550nm at 1 Joule of energy incident on a square centimeter over a time period of 10 seconds or less. Put a different way, if considering a 10-second exposure, the incident intensity must be less than 100mW/cm2. The transmitted LCRD wavelengths are near 1550nm and, as such, fall within this eye-safe portion of the spectrum.

For NASA programs transmitting a laser through navigable airspace, coordination with the FAA is required. The laser operator must contact the FAA regional service center responsible for the airspace in question and obtain a Letter of Determination stating that the FAA does not object to the laser operations. The process for getting a Letter of Determination is outlined in FAA JO 7400.2K and in FAA Advisory Circular 70-1. The laser operator must submit the details of the laser and the control measures that will ensure that aircraft are not illuminated by lasers in excess of the MPE.

The FAA regional service center will assess the potential of

the laser system to present a hazard to aircraft based on the calculations outlined in ANSI Z136.6. If no potential hazard is found, a Letter of No Objection will be issued. If, however, it is determined that the laser will exceed the MPE within navigable airspace, the FAA regional service center will examine the laser system's control measures. These control measures may include human aircraft spotters, radar systems, automated laser shutters, and laser pointing restrictions – measures which can be expensive and may constrain operations significantly [6].

Until recently, the FAA directed the regional service centers to refer to Aerospace Standard 6029: **Performance Criteria for Laser Control Measures Used for Aviation Safety** (also a product of the SAE G10-T Committee) when evaluating the proposed control measures for a laser system. AS-6029 outlines under which circumstances control measures are warranted and provides guidelines for their implementation. When AS-6029 is applied to lasers in the eye-safe portion of the spectrum, consideration of a 10-second exposure is required when calculating the MPE. This means that any laser at 1550nm wavelength with an intensity greater than 100mW/cm² will exceed the MPE and thus will require control measures to ensure it doesn't illuminate aircraft.

It was later recognized that an accidental 10-second exposure of a moving aircraft is not realistic and is overly restrictive. In May 2013 the SAE G10-T committee released an updated document, AS-6029-A. This update recognizes that inadvertent exposure of aircraft will be fleeting due to their speed. AS-6029-A reduces from 10 seconds to 0.25 seconds the exposure duration that needs to be considered when determining if the laser exceeds the MPE. This effectively increases by a factor of 40 the intensity at which an eye-safe wavelength laser exceeds the MPE. The intensity required to deposit 1 Joule per square cm in 0.25 seconds is 4 Watts/cm², compared to the previous 100mW/cm² limit for a 10-second exposure.

The FAA has advised its regional service centers to refer to AS-6029-A when making a determination; however, the FAA has yet to reference AS-6029-A in its official documents. Until AS-6029-A is officially accepted by the FAA, there is some risk that the FAA could, with little notice, revert back to the earlier version of the document.

5. THE LASER CLEARINGHOUSE (LCH) AND PREDICTIVE AVOIDANCE

With the increasing outdoor use of Lasers comes the risk of inadvertently irradiating a satellite. Unintentional irradiation of a satellite could have serious consequences: Such an accident could damage sensitive instruments or could even cause an international incident.

In order to reduce the possibility of U.S. Department of Defense laser projects accidentally illuminating satellites, the Laser ClearingHouse (LCH) was established. All Department of Defense laser programs operating to, in, through, or from

space – or aimed above the horizon – are required to coordinate operations with the LCH by **DoD Instruction 3100.11: *Illumination of Objects in Space by Lasers***.

The LCH also allows non-DoD civilian laser programs to coordinate their operations with it as LCH resources allow. While not under DoD authority, NASA Procedural Requirements NPR 8715.5A mandate that all NASA laser programs coordinate with the LCH.

6. LCRD AND THE LCH PROCESS

LCRD started working closely with the LCH early in the program in order to evaluate how LCH restrictions could impact all planned laser links. The first step in the LCH process is to submit a Laser Registration Form which outlines all relevant laser parameters. The LCH then reviews this information and makes a determination as to whether the laser operations pose a threat to satellites. If the laser system is found not to pose a threat, a waiver can be given by the LCH and no further coordination with the LCH is required. Operation of a laser project that is not given a waiver requires submitting to the LCH a schedule listing planned laser sources, their targets, and their planned times of operation.

The LCH analyzes this information to evaluate whether a satellite will enter a pre-determined hazard zone – a cone around the laser beam that represents the pointing uncertainty of the laser beam. (The standard Keep-Out-Cone assigned is ~2.5° half angle but can be as small as 0.1° if it can be demonstrated that the pointing uncertainty of the laser will be under 0.1°.) The LCH returns a list of Predictive Avoidance (PA) windows – times during which the laser must be shuttered.

LCRD submitted registration forms for the planned space and ground terminals. After review by the LCH, it was determined that the LCRD space and ground terminals could not be waived and would need to coordinate operations with the LCH. In order to assess the impact the LCH windows would have on operations, the program requested simulated PA window lists for various operational scenarios.

7. LCRD OPERATIONAL SCENARIOS

The LCH worked with the LCRD program to generate simulated PA window lists for four communication links: Ground to Geosynchronous Satellite (Alphasat), Geosynchronous Satellite (Alphasat) to Ground, Low Earth Orbit (International Space Station) to Geosynchronous Satellite, and Geosynchronous Satellite (Alphasat) to Low Earth Orbit (International Space Station). For each of these scenarios, a PA window list was generated for a 3-day period for several different Keep-Out-Cone angles.

Of these four scenarios, it was initially found that only the Geosynchronous Satellite to the International Space Station resulted in a large enough number of closed PA windows to make a communications link impractical. The large number outages for the GEO to LEO leg of the relay is the result of the minimum 0.1° Keep-Out-Cone. For the GEO to LEO leg,

a 0.1° Keep-Out-Cone is approximately 140 km in diameter. Further complicating the matter is the fact that this cone is tracking a LEO moving rapidly over the Earth. If a satellite enters this volume as it sweeps through LEO, the result will be a closed window: The simulations found on the order of hundreds of closures over the course of the 3-day simulation period.

Fortunately, recent refinements in the LCH calculations have removed this source of outages for LCRD. Specifically, the LCH now incorporates a maximum hazard range for the laser system in question. The LCH now analyzes the laser characteristics and determines the range at which the beam poses no threat to orbital assets, effectively truncating the Keep-Out-Cone at this range. In the case of the LCRD space terminal at Geosynchronous Orbit, the maximum hazard range was determined to fall far short of the densely populated LEO space. This eliminates the vast majority of PA outages and makes the GEO-LEO communications link practical.

While coordination with the LCH will be required for LCRD, it will not prevent the mission from accomplishing its goals. Further work with the LCH will be necessary to define a plan of operations that ensures adherence to the PA windows issued for the LCRD mission.

8. SUMMARY

Optical Communications is an important communications technology for future space missions. It has the potential of providing user data rates well in excess of what is possible with today's RF technology; furthermore, the user burden in terms of mass, power, and volume should be less even for data rates comparable to today's RF systems. While the capacity of current and near-term RF communications technology is still increasing, it is eventually limited by bandwidth allocation restrictions, power requirements, flight terminal antenna size, and weight limitations.

Future optical communications links to and from space will need to be compliant with policies and regulations issued by both the U.S. Federal Aviation Administration and the U.S. Laser Clearinghouse. NASA will test out operational concepts compliant with the FAA and LCH through its Laser Communications Relay Demonstration.

While there is still a lot to learn, NASA believes that it will be able to develop mission critical operational concepts and procedures for this new communications technology area.

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BIOGRAPHIES

Bernard L. Edwards is the Chief Communications Systems Engineer at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center. He received a B.S. in Electrical Engineering in 1989, a M.S. in Electrical Engineering in 1991, and a M.S. in Computer Science in 1993 all from the Johns Hopkins University. He supports the NASA representative to the Interagency Operations Advisory Group (IOAG), and leads NASA's team in the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS) in the area of optical communications. He has been involved in various NASA optical communication projects and technology developments since coming to NASA in 2000. He is currently the Chief Engineer for the Laser Communications Relay Demonstration Project.

Robert E. Lafon is an Optical Physicist at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center working on the Laser Communications Relay Demonstration Project. He previously worked on the Lunar Laser Communication Demonstration project. He received a B.S. in Physics from the University of Texas at Austin. He did his Graduate work at the State University of New York at Stony Brook researching ionization processes in extremely intense laser fields.

Edward Y. Luzhansky is the Physicist at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center. He received B.S. in Optics from the St. Petersburg Institute of Precision Mechanics and Optics, M.S. in Electrical Engineering from the University of Connecticut. He is member of NASA Optical Communications team in the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS). He has been involved in development and demonstration of various tactical and space-based Optical Communication Systems. He is currently Optical Communications Mission System Engineer on the Laser Communications Relay Demonstration Project.